

DEVELOPING ENGAGING ENGINEERING EDUCATION RESOURCES BASED ON STUDENTS LEARNING AND EDUCATORS' TEACHING STYLES

S. Chakrabarti¹

ANSYS, Inc.
Canonsburg, PA, USA
0000-0002-8267-1064

C. Fredriksson

ANSYS UK LTD.
Cambridge, UK

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Teaching methods

Keywords: teaching resources, engineering education, learning styles, teaching styles, project-based learning

ABSTRACT

The learning styles of engineering students have evolved over the years with the advent of technology-enhanced education. Educators have also changed their teaching styles to incorporate student-centric pedagogy and educational technology. While the COVID-19 pandemic proliferated online teaching worldwide, often forcing educators to conceptualize and convert face-to-face teaching materials to online learning modules, Ansys academic endeavours have also pivoted to support educators and digital learning. This paper highlights the Ansys Education Resources, aimed at helping undergraduate materials and simulation-based design educators teach and inspire students. These are also perfect for students and self-learners who are looking to complement classroom content. Moreover, these help professors in assigning supplemental homework or capstone projects.

The resources, of which 80% are openly accessed, are categorized as lectures, case studies, micro-projects, exercises, etc., and make the educators' job easier in inspiring and engaging the students' digital learning process throughout the undergraduate curricula. Solutions to exercises and projects are restricted to educators with current Granta EduPack product licenses. In developing these resources, the content developers consider different teaching and learning styles with special emphasis on project-based learning and incorporating questions that inspire students to consider societal impact and ethical choices. Some resources are purposely prepared for discussions and debates.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
S. Chakrabarti; soma.chakrabarti@ansys.com

The impact of these resources is measured through qualitative questions-answers in user group meetings, periodical surveys, and quantitative performance (such as download numbers) of the website repositories.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Learning Styles of Students and Teaching Styles of Professors in Engineering

Students learn in diverse ways, depending on their own learning styles, but also depending on the discipline of study. The teachers should be adapting to such learning styles by designing appropriate teaching resources and picking up the appropriate style to instruct a specific group of students. The learning styles of engineering students have often been described as visual [1, 2, 3]; however, with the advent of digital communication systems, students lean on receiving information via digital media, with the ability of interacting with such material in different ways. In undergraduate engineering education, however, little has changed in classroom teaching to inspire students with these evolving learning preferences until the Coronavirus pandemic in 2020. Within a couple of weeks, sometimes even shorter, universities and colleges worldwide had to transfer in-person classes to remote teaching, often to live online classes or video-based asynchronous learning. Online flipped classrooms where students studied on their own and then joined live online discussions proliferated. However, the effort was more of a reactive response than a thoughtful, pro-active approach.

1.2. Teaching Resources for Visual, Interactive and Digital Learning

Preparing visually attractive, interactive, engaging teaching resources in digital format is not easy. For more than 10 years, the Education Division of Granta Design in the UK has been preparing such resources to help the teachers that will inspire materials education. Since 2019, after its acquisition by Ansys, this team expanded and are also engaged in preparing resources for simulation-based design and other engineering disciplines. This paper presents a few of those examples with relationships to how students can learn and how professors can teach in digital mode, using such resources, without losing interactivity or engagement in a virtual or an in-person classroom.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 First, Make it Visual

It is no secret that a picture speaks a thousand words. When Dr. Mike Ashby, a professor at the University of Cambridge and co-founder of Granta Design, Ltd. started working on such resources, visual appeal to engineering students, through appropriate animated slides, was one of the primary concerns. Resources were made where an educator would simply use one slide to describe a complex phenomenon, a concept, or seed a debate in the classroom.

2.2 Second, Make it Interactive

Sets of interactive learning resources were prepared for students in Adobe Flash, which have recently been changed into interactive PowerPoint slideshows that students could easily play with and learn from, and thus be inspired to learn more.

2.3 Third, Make it Thought-Provoking and Engaging

Today's students are well informed and genuinely want to contribute to the sustainability of earth and consequently to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals that the United Nations has set forth in Agenda 2030. The resources have embedded examples that provoke such conversations and engage the students.

2.4 Fourth, Make it a Package to Help in Teaching

We know from analytics that professors extensively use lecture notes, quizzes, exercises, micro-projects, case study-based projects, etc., to help students learn. So, the team has prepared teaching packages exclusively for professors, providing solutions to the exercises, quizzes and microprojects that the students cannot access. This helps new teachers and experienced professors alike to spend less time in creating examples and frees up more time to prepare for teaching.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Visually Engaging and Interactive Resources: An Example

Material Selection: Screening

Unbiased selection requires that all materials are considered to be candidates until shown to be otherwise. Using the steps in the boxes on the figure on the right:

The process of these **screening**, eliminates candidates that cannot do the job at all because one or more of their attributes lies outside the limits set by the constraints. As examples the requirement that "the component must function in boiling water", or that "the component must be transparent" imposes obvious limits on the attributes of maximum service temperature and optical transparency that successful candidates must meet. We refer to these as attribute limits.

However in this case there is no need to screen prospective materials.

Screening

Screening requires a set of 'go'/no go' criteria which can be applied to the set of prospective materials. Which of the constraints **stated** in the translation can be used to screen possible materials?

- Resist UV
- Necessary toughness
- Must not fail in high winds
- Function from -40° C to -40° C

- Resist corrosion in marine environment
- Resist UV
- Must not buckle
- Necessary toughness

- Resist corrosion in marine environment
- Resist UV
- Necessary toughness
- Function from -40° C to -40° C

Correct!

Fig.1 Students can click a box to assess knowledge Fig. 2 The test takes to right or wrong answer

3.2 Complete Teaching Packages

Presentation slides with notes

Phase Fractions within Systems

Understanding what phases will be found at specific composition and temperature is knowledge important for alloy development

Micro-projects and Solutions

Quizzes and Solutions

Exercises and Solutions

Concept Maps to help students understand the connections among phase diagram terms

Fig. 3 A complete introductory teaching resource package contains lecture notes, micro-projects, concept maps and exercises besides other components.

3.3 Measure of Success: Quantitative

The team measured the likability and usage of every resource on the website [4]. Among the unrestricted access resources, visually appealing, active learning-inducing infographics had highest download of 11957 in the 2-year period examined, followed by booklets, such as Material Property Data for Engineering Materials, with 10460 downloads. All interactive examples and advanced industrial case studies (often used for final or capstone projects) had high download numbers, around 7000-8000, with the Industrial Case Study on Automotive Door Panel having the highest amongst those (8289).

3.4 Measure of Success: Qualitative

The team held a number of Users Group Meetings (UGMs) and surveys to know the usage of the resources and ways to make those better. From these UGMs, it was clear that professors were keen on using the, so called, advanced case studies, whereas the students preferred engaging, interactive, colourful documents. In recent years, there is an increase in requests for sustainability related resources that also include societal impacts from materials sourcing, product manufacturing, design, supply chain management and reuse of products.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Addressing students' learning styles during teaching, thus adapting to a teaching style that engages students is essential. Today's students, especially those who study engineering, are digitally savvy and environmentally and socially conscious. A variety of teaching resources show that addressing all of these is possible through thoughtfully crafted, visually and interactively engaging and scientifically accurate resources that, based on the content, can be used for teaching and learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jamali, A. and Mohamad M. (2018), Dimension of Learning Style among Engineering Students, *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series*, 1049 012055 doi :10.1088/1742-6596/1049/1/012055.
- [2] Felder, R. (1988), Learning and Teaching Styles in Engineering Students, *Engineering Education*, Vol. 78(7), pp. 674-681.
- [3] Balfaqeeh, M. (2017) Understanding Engineering Students' Learning Styles, *International Journal of Linguistics and Communication*, Vol. 5(1), pp. 44-55.
- [4] Website: www.ansys.com/education-resources, accessed 30 April 2022.